

AquaPLAN

Aquatic Pollution from Light and
Anthropogenic Noise: **Management
of Impacts on Biodiversity**

Report on policy instruments for managing the impacts of LNP on aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem services (including recommended best practice)

31/12/25 Version 2.6

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

SCIENTIFIC OVERVIEW

Artificial light at night (ALAN) and anthropogenic underwater noise are **increasingly recognised as significant** but under-regulated threats to aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. Both pollutants have the **potential to disrupt behaviour, physiology, population dynamics and ecological interactions across marine and freshwater organisms**, yet their management within policy frameworks remains uneven and incomplete.

Across the EU, **legislation for managing underwater noise** is comparatively **more well-developed than that for ALAN in the marine environment**: the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) explicitly addresses noise under Descriptor 11, requiring Member States to monitor acoustic pressures, maintain noise registries, and implement mitigation measures. In contrast, regulatory coverage for noise in freshwater habitats remains restricted to generic environmental legislation that lacks these specific mandates. Binding EU-wide thresholds for continuous and impulsive noise introduced under the Zero Pollution Action Plan represent a major step forward, though enforcement and harmonised implementation remain insufficient. Regional seas conventions such as OSPAR and the Barcelona Convention, and international agreements including the Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic area (ACCOBAMS), the Agreement on the Conservation of Small Cetaceans of the Baltic, North East Atlantic, Irish and North Seas (ASCOBANS), the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) guidelines, further provide detailed technical guidance for noise monitoring and mitigation, primarily focused on protecting cetaceans but increasingly extending to broader biodiversity.

In contrast, light pollution remains largely absent from binding aquatic legislation. While ALAN is acknowledged as a biodiversity pressure in emerging EU policies, including the Nature Restoration Regulation, Zero Pollution Agenda, and the Light Pollution Manifesto, there are no EU-level thresholds, standards, or formal MSFD requirements. Only a few Member States reference light in their Programmes of Measures, and actions remain voluntary, fragmented, and limited in scope. Internationally, recognition of ALAN is growing, marked by CMS decisions and the recent launch of the UN-endorsed Global Ocean Artificial Light at Night Network (GOALANN), but regulatory mechanisms lag far behind those for noise.

Freshwater governance tools, particularly the Water Framework Directive, offer potential pathways to manage LNP where ecological impacts are demonstrated, but explicit provisions remain undeveloped. Natura 2000 obligations under the Habitats and Birds Directives can serve as important leverage points, as shown in legal precedents requiring Member States to address light disturbance affecting protected species.

Overall, **governance** of underwater noise is **progressing** toward **structured, enforceable management**, whereas regulation of aquatic light pollution is at an early stage, with **clear gaps in monitoring, thresholds, and mandatory mitigation**.

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Key **needs** across both pollutant types include:

- i) harmonised monitoring standards,
- ii) integration into marine spatial planning and impact assessments,
- iii) binding ecological thresholds for ALAN,
- iv) improved enforcement of existing noise measures, and
- v) mechanisms linking LNP reduction to restoration and conservation objectives.

Strengthening these policy instruments is essential for safeguarding aquatic ecosystems as human activities continue to intensify across Europe's marine and freshwater environments.

THE ROLE OF DELIVERABLE 2.5

Bridging the gap between the existing policy landscape and the needs of aquatic ecosystems is the central function of AquaPLAN policy deliverables.

Building on the legal and policy database developed under previous Deliverable D2.4, this report provides an integrated assessment of the effectiveness, coherence, and practical implementation of Light and Noise Pollution (LNP) management instruments relevant to aquatic ecosystems across the EU and internationally. Together, D2.4 and D2.5 offer a comprehensive and actionable foundation for improving policy responses to LNP across jurisdictions. D2.5 represents the completion of milestone 6 of AquaPLAN.

The recommendations and best practices documented here will directly inform the later experimental work and the development of mitigation and planning tools within the AquaPLAN project. This deliverable also contributes directly to aligning AquaPLAN outputs with the complementary policy work undertaken in the PLAN-B project (thanks to the joint coauthorship represented by Yana Yakushina).

By clarifying best-practice approaches and identifying regulatory gaps specifically relevant to aquatic environments, this deliverable provides an essential foundation for the subsequent PLAN-B policy briefs on light and noise pollution (D4.1 and D4.2). Together, the two projects form a coordinated policy pathway: AquaPLAN synthesises the aquatic-focused evidence base and policy instruments, while PLAN-B extends this analysis to terrestrial systems and broader regulatory synergies. This structured progression ensures that both projects collectively support a coherent, cross-ecosystem policy framework for managing LNP, enabling later joint outputs—such as PLAN-B D4.3 and D4.4 and AquaPLAN D6.5 and D6.7—to rest on fully harmonised and mutually reinforcing analyses.

Disclaimer: The document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including its associated Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

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ABBREVIATIONS USED IN THE TEXT

ACCOBAMS: Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and Contiguous Atlantic Area

ALAN: Artificial Light At Night

ASCOBANS: Agreement on the Conservation of Small Cetaceans of the Baltic, North East Atlantic, Irish and North Seas

CBD: Convention on Biological Diversity

CMS: Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals

COM: European Commission legislative proposal reference (e.g., COM(2020) 380, COM/2021/400)

COP: Conference of the Parties

D11: Descriptor 11 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive

EIA: Environmental Impact Assessment

END: Environmental Noise Directive

EO11: Ecological Objective 11 (Energy, including underwater noise, under the Barcelona Convention)

EU: European Union

EEA-JRC: European Environment Agency – Joint Research Centre

GBF: Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

GES: Good Environmental Status

GOALANN: Global Ocean Artificial Light at Night Network

IUCN: International Union for Conservation of Nature

IWC: International Whaling Commission

IMO: International Maritime Organization

LNP: Light and Noise Pollution

LP: Light Pollution

MEPC: Marine Environment Protection Committee (IMO)

MoP: Meeting of the Parties

MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive

MSPD: Marine Spatial Planning Directive

NP: Noise Pollution

NRP: National Restoration Plan

NRR: Nature Restoration Regulation

PoMs: Programmes of Measures

SACs: Special Areas of Conservation (Habitats Directive)

ScC-SC5: Sessional Committee of the CMS Scientific Council, 5th Meeting

SPAs: Special Protection Areas (Birds Directive)

UNCLOS: United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea

UNEP: United Nations Environmental Programme

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

US: United States

WFD: Water Framework Directive

ZPAP: Zero Pollution Action Plan

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1. INTRODUCTION

The **world has become a brighter and noisier place over recent decades**, with artificial light and noise disrupting aquatic environments (Duarte et al., 2021, Marangoni et al., 2022; Peng et al., 2015; Hölker et al., 2024). Our oceans, lakes, and waterways are already subject to intense human use, and as population growth and resource demands continue to rise, pressures on these systems are expected to intensify. Activities on land and in the water can impact aquatic species, communities and ecosystems. Two **emerging anthropogenic threats** to aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity are **light pollution** (LP), caused by artificial light at night (ALAN), and **underwater noise** (noise pollution, NP).

For the purposes of this report:

- a) **regulatory instruments** are understood to include **all primary sources of law and policy**, such as laws, directives, regulations, resolutions, and action plans, adopted to regulate the conduct of individuals, businesses, or government agencies.
- b) **Aquatic light pollution** is defined as the introduction of excess ALAN from human sources (like coastal lights, ports, boats) which disrupt natural light-dark cycles, while **aquatic noise pollution** is defined as the introduction of excessive, human-generated sounds (like shipping, sonar, construction) into water environments. Both phenomena have negative and disrupting consequences for marine and freshwater biodiversity.

ALAN affects 22% of the world's coastlines (Davies et al., 2014), with 1.9 million km² of coastal seas exposed to biologically important ALAN, decreasing to 1.6 million km² at 10 m and 0.8 million km² at 20 m (Smyth et al., 2021). Marine ALAN can come from a variety of onshore and offshore sources, including towns and cities, ports and harbours, shipping, oil and gas platforms and light-induced fisheries (Davies et al., 2014). Freshwater ecosystems may be even more impacted (Hölker et al., 2023), with freshwater shorelines often highly urbanised and over half of the world's population living within 3 km of freshwater (Kummu et al. 2021).

From circadian rhythms to lunar and seasonal cycles, light is known to drive metabolic and physiological pathways and behaviour in individuals (Gaston et al., 2015), with ALAN disrupting these cycles and altering behaviour in a wide range of organisms from aquatic microorganisms to mammals and plants (Hölker et al., 2023, Stanton and Cowart, 2024). This disruption occurs globally and is associated with changes in species abundance and community composition (Marangoni et al., 2022).

Anthropogenic underwater noise is another pollutant that is receiving increasing attention, with sources including shipping, fishing and boating activities, oil exploration, military sonar, dredging and the development of offshore renewable energy installations (Chahouri et al., 2022). **Underwater noise first became recognised as an issue in the 1980s**, when concern arose that commercial activities in the marine environment, such as offshore oil and gas extraction, could disturb marine mammals (Turl, 1982), whilst these animals appeared to acclimate to and seek out slow-moving small vessels (Dahlheim et al., 1981).

Whilst early research focussed on the impact of underwater noise on marine mammals (Turl, 1982), underwater noise has more recently been shown to impact a wide range of aquatic

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animals across all trophic levels in both freshwater and marine habitats (El-Dairi et al., 2024). Furthermore, underwater noise pollution is increasingly known to cause not only species-level effects, but population and ecosystem-level alterations (Di Franco et al., 2020). Importantly, sound in the aquatic environment is formed of two components (sound pressure and particle motion). Aquatic mammals detect the pressure component of sound, invertebrates are impacted by particle motion, and fish can be affected by either component (Hawkins et al., 2021).

Light and noise pollution (LNP) have gradually been recognised as forms of environmental pollution and as significant stressors within the aquatic environment (Davies et al., 2020, Hölker et al., 2023, Rountree et al., 2020), with subsequent growing attention on the political agenda. Noise is listed under Description 11 (energy in the environment) of the MSFD, and there is a push towards adding light to this legislation. However, despite several decades of research documenting their harmful effects, **regulatory action to mitigate these pollutants remains relatively limited.** Both forms of pollution continue to intensify, adding further pressure to already vulnerable aquatic ecosystems. They are still **widely regarded as ‘forgotten’ or neglected pollutants** (Science and Technology Committee, 2023), receiving far less regulatory scrutiny than more conventional forms of pollution, such as chemical, atmospheric, or water pollution.

This report provides an overview of existing international, European, and national regulatory initiatives aimed at addressing light and noise pollution in European aquatic habitats. It outlines the current regulatory landscape, supported by selected case examples and a brief historical context, and concludes with recommendations for strengthening future policy and governance frameworks.

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2. DATA AND METHODS

This report employs a **range of approaches** to provide an overview of regulatory action addressing LNP in aquatic habitats. A **literature review** serves as the primary method, offering insights into the current state of research on LNP impacts, existing regulatory measures, potential mitigation solutions, and emerging policy recommendations. In parallel, a **legal and regulatory analysis** (following a **positivist approach**) is undertaken to identify and examine the relevant provisions contained within the selected regulatory instruments.

The identification and selection of these regulatory instruments were conducted using a **semi-systematic search strategy**. The regulatory frameworks were searched for using the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) databases of environmental law (<https://www.ecolex.org/> and <https://www.fao.org/faolex/en/>). The following Boolean search terms were used, namely 'light pollution' OR 'artificial light' AND 'marine' OR 'freshwater' OR 'aquatic', to identify frameworks for managing aquatic light pollution; and the search terms 'anthropogenic noise' OR 'underwater noise' AND 'marine' OR 'freshwater' OR 'aquatic', were used to identify the regulatory frameworks applicable for noise pollution.

Another implemented method was the **snowballing technique** to search online, including searching regional seas websites such as the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic ([OSPAR](#)) and the [Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission](#) (HELCOM) commissions, to **find other regulatory documents**. Relevant legal frameworks were input into a database, which was organised into international, European, Regional Seas and national sections (**Deliverable 2.4** "Database of LNP pollution impacts on aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem services"⁵). The database describes the document type, the date of adoption, whether it focuses on marine or freshwater habitats (or both), and provides a brief description and any potential stakeholders. Additionally, **other regulatory databases and reports**, focusing on LNP regulations **were searched**, in particular Dark Sky International and the University of Arizona LP Legal database (<https://idadb.cals.arizona.edu/>) and the International Astronomical Union Centre for the Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky from Satellite Constellation Interference (IAU CPS) Report on the National Approaches to the Protection of Dark and Quiet Skies (<https://zenodo.org/records/14566125>).

The primary focus was placed **on documents available in English** and on regulatory frameworks **explicitly referring to LNP**. However, to ensure a broader and more representative understanding of current regulatory approaches, **selected national examples** in other languages were also examined. This was particularly important given that most regulatory action to address LNP is implemented at the national level. In addition, the report considers **regulatory instruments that do not explicitly mention LNP but** are nonetheless **potentially applicable** to addressing these issues in aquatic habitats.

To complement these methods and get insights specifically for the **European scale**, the **Descriptor 11 (D11)** of the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive** (Directive 2008/56/EC)

⁵<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e51eb9497f&appId=PPGMS>

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(MSFD) was examined. The MSFD provides for Member States to establish, implement and report their **Programmes of Measures (PoMs)** to achieve or maintain Good Environmental Status in their marine waters. These documents were analysed to get additional policy insights on aquatic habitats conservation (via the EIONET portal (<https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/msfd/>)). For each PoM examined, it was recorded whether the measure addressed light and/or noise pollution and categorised the type of action involved, such as monitoring, mitigation, regulatory intervention, or capacity-building. This analysis contributed to a more comprehensive understanding of how European marine governance currently integrates, or overlooks, LNP considerations. An additional data source for European regulatory instruments was the Official Journal of the European Union, accessed via EUR-Lex (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html>), which provided authoritative texts of relevant legislation and policy documents.

The **methods and data sources outlined above form the foundation for the analysis** presented in this report. Accordingly, the **report examines international, Regional Seas, EU, and selected national regulatory frameworks**, such as directives, regulations, resolutions, and action plans, that are applicable to the management of LNP in aquatic environments.

The report is structured around the **following key research questions**:

- What regulatory frameworks currently exist to address LNP in aquatic habitats?
- Which aquatic ecosystems and species are the primary focus of these regulatory instruments?
- How comprehensive are the governance frameworks for European waters in addressing aquatic LNP?
- What key regulatory gaps can be identified, and what recommendations emerge from this analysis?

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3. HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

Despite a long-standing scientific interest in the impacts of light and noise pollution, the corresponding regulatory efforts remain uneven and have been evolving differently.

Noise pollution has a considerably longer regulatory history than light pollution, largely due to the nature of the pollutant itself. As with many other forms of pollution, early regulatory efforts emerged in response to human disturbance, reflecting a distinctly anthropocentric approach to governance. Noise has been perceived as a nuisance for millennia, which facilitated the development of measures to limit its disruptive effects. Notably, the first documented noise regulation dates back to 44 BCE, when the Roman Emperor Julius Caesar prohibited wheeled vehicles from operating within city limits between sunset and sunrise (Lee and Warhol, 2024). These early interventions, however, were concerned exclusively with protecting human wellbeing.

From the **late twentieth century** onwards, NP began to be recognised not merely as a source of human annoyance but **as an environmental stressor** with significant impacts on habitats and biodiversity, an awareness that became particularly evident at the national level. As international environmental law gradually shifted towards a more ecocentric orientation, states increasingly viewed various forms of nuisance, including noise pollution, as environmental rather than solely social concerns (Richardson, 2016). Anthropogenic underwater noise has been recognised as an established threat to aquatic biota, although this awareness has primarily grown from the co-occurrence of mass strandings of marine mammals and impulsive noise such as sonars or military activity (Chou et al., 2021). This shift was reflected in regulatory developments such as the inclusion of anthropogenic ocean noise within the U.S. Marine Mammal Protection Act in 1981 (McCarthy and Lichtman, 2007).

At the **international level**, a pivotal milestone was the adoption of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) in 1982, which defined marine pollution as *“the introduction by man, directly or indirectly, of substances or energy into the marine environment (...) resulting in deleterious effects”* (UNCLOS, 1982). The explicit reference to energy as a potential pollutant laid the foundation for later recognition of underwater noise as a form of marine pollution. This framing has since informed a growing number of international environmental instruments, as reflected in contemporary assessments and policy discussions on underwater noise (Thomsen et al., 2021). For instance, the 1996 Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and Contiguous Atlantic Area (ACCOBAMS, 1996) formally recognised underwater noise as a significant threat and has adopted a series of guidelines on this issue since at least 2004, beginning with Resolution 2.16, which addressed the assessment of anthropogenic noise. Similarly, the 1979 Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS, 1979) identified underwater noise as a serious threat to marine species in 2008 during its Ninth Conference of the Parties (UNEP/CMS/COP9/REPORT). At this meeting, Parties adopted Resolution 9.19 *“Adverse Anthropogenic Marine/Ocean Noise Impacts on Cetaceans and Other Biota”* (CMS, 2009), mandating further investigation into the impacts of anthropogenic noise on cetaceans and other marine organisms. This CMS initiative contributed to elevating underwater noise on both international and national policy agendas and helped stimulate the gradual development of measures aimed at mitigating the ecological impacts of underwater noise pollution.

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ACCOBAMS-MOP5/2013/Doc22Rev1

Figure 1: Summary of the regulatory developments at the international level to address anthropogenic noise impacts on the marine environment (between 1998 and 2013). Source: Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and Contiguous Atlantic Area. (2014). Submission to MCBEM-2014-01: Addressing marine noise pollution (page 8)⁶.

By contrast, the **development of LP regulation** has progressed far **more slowly** than that of NP. This disparity is closely linked to the **nature of ALAN**. Whereas **noise** is generally perceived as **undesirable** and inherently intrusive, **ALAN** is widely associated with **comfort, safety, and well-being**. This positive societal perception has been one of the primary obstacles to recognising LP as an environmental problem and to advancing its regulation (Hölker et al. 2010; Cieraad and Dalley, 2025).

Early advocacy for LP controls originated within the **astronomical community**, which was among the first to experience the direct consequences of the disappearing night sky. Accordingly, the earliest regulatory measures were motivated by the need to protect

⁶ <https://www.cbd.int/doc/meetings/mar/mcbem-2014-01/other/mcbem-2014-01-submission-accobams-03-en.pdf>

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astronomical observation. A landmark example is the world's first law restricting commercial searchlights, adopted in 1958 in Flagstaff, Arizona (US), to safeguard the night sky for local observatories (Yakushina, 2025b). Such astronomy-driven initiatives **stimulated further regulatory action** in other regions hosting major observatories, including Spain's 1988 Law on the Protection of the Astronomical Quality of the Observatories of the Institute of Astrophysics of the Canary Islands (Spain, 1988).

Over time, however, an expanding body of scientific research has demonstrated that ALAN poses significant risks not only to astronomy but also to ecosystems and biodiversity. This growing evidence base has **gradually shifted** the discourse from an astronomy-centred concern to a **broader environmental and ecological one**, highlighting the need for more comprehensive regulatory responses (Hölker et al. 2021).

The **first major international framework** to address LP as an environmental concern emerged under the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS). **ALAN was explicitly recognised as a pollutant** for the first time during the adoption of *Decision 12.17 on Marine Turtles at the Twelfth Meeting of the Conference of the Parties (COP12)*, held in Manila, the Philippines, in 2017 (UNEP/CMS/COP12/Decision; Yakushina, 2022). Building on this initial acknowledgement, the **Global Ocean Artificial Light at Night Network (GOALANN)** was launched at the United Nations Ocean Decade Conference in April 2024, marking the **UN's first formal recognition of ALAN as an emerging marine pollutant of global concern**. GOALANN unites research groups worldwide to create a central hub of expertise, data, and tools on marine LP. Its overarching aim is to make scientific knowledge accessible to policymakers, environmental managers, maritime industries, and the wider public, thereby supporting evidence-informed actions to prevent or reduce light-induced harm to ocean ecosystems. The network's endorsement under the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030) further underscores both the growing visibility of ALAN as a pollutant and the need for coordinated global efforts to understand and mitigate its effects.

At the **European level**, LNP have also begun to attract increasing attention, although noise has generally received greater regulatory focus to date. European shelf seas rank among the brightest and noisiest marine environments on the planet (AquaPLAN Visualisation Portal: <https://aquaplan.eofrom.space/>). The Mediterranean Sea is one of the most intensely exposed coastal regions to ALAN globally (Marangoni et al., 2022), driven by dense coastal populations and high levels of tourism (Peregrym et al., 2020). Meanwhile, the North Sea experiences significant light and noise exposure from both coastal and offshore sources, largely due to its high concentration of maritime traffic and offshore infrastructure (Aulinger et al., 2016; Martins et al., 2023). Similarly, many European lakes and rivers are highly affected by ALAN (Jechow & Hölker 2019; e.g., Lake Geneva and Lake Vanern, as a result of the artificial sky brightness arriving at the surface of the lake and by noise pollution (e.g., Lake IJsselmeer, due to high shipping density (AquaPLAN Visualisation Portal: <https://aquaplan.eofrom.space/>)).

With respect to regulatory frameworks, the principal **EU instrument** directly addressing environmental noise is the **Environmental Noise Directive (END)** (2002/49/EC), which aims to prevent and **reduce the harmful effects of noise**. By contrast, **LP** has not been explicitly regulated at the EU level. It has only received indirect recognition: the **Nature Restoration**

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Regulation (2024/1991) refers to LP in its preamble, encouraging Member States to “consider stopping, reducing, or remediating light pollution in all ecosystems” (NRR, 2024). Although non-binding in nature, this acknowledgement marks a notable shift towards the inclusion of LP within the broader EU environmental policy agenda.

Despite recent regulatory developments, these pollutants are still frequently described as the ‘forgotten’ or neglected pollutants (Science and Technology Committee, 2023) and remain significantly less regulated than more established categories of pollution, such as chemical or plastic pollution.

4. INTERNATIONAL REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS

The international level represents the **highest level of regulatory governance**, shaping and facilitating national regulatory developments. International instruments play a **crucial role in guiding states to take action** on a wide range of environmental issues, including light and noise pollution. This **section examines the key international frameworks that directly or indirectly addresses LNP in aquatic environments**.

4.1 NOISE POLLUTION

The **International Whaling Commission (IWC)** was the **first international marine framework** to identify and **recognise anthropogenic noise** as one of the priority topics for research and **directed funding toward addressing** its impacts on cetaceans (Resolution 1998-6 "Resolution on Environmental Change and Cetaceans" (IWC, 1998). This action facilitated further developments.

Following this political action, the **Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and Contiguous Atlantic Area (ACCOBAMS)** was the **first marine international framework** to develop **guidelines for underwater noise** in 2004, also recognising it as a threat to cetaceans ([Resolution 2.16](#)). ACCOBAMS has a range including the maritime waters of the Black Sea, the Mediterranean Sea, and the contiguous Atlantic area west of the Straits of Gibraltar, including the Pelagos Sanctuary. They have since further strengthened their commitments to address underwater noise through a number of resolutions: [Resolution 3.10](#) (2007) *Guidelines to Address the Impact of Anthropogenic Noise on Marine Mammals in the ACCOBAMS Area*, [Resolution 4.17](#) (2010) *Further Actions to Minimize the Impact of Anthropogenic Noise on Cetaceans*, [Resolution 5.15](#) (2013) *Underwater Noise Mitigation Measures and Methodological Guide*, [Resolution 6.17](#) (2016) *Implementation of Noise Mitigation Measures and Monitoring Strategies*, [Resolution 6.18](#) (2016) *Mediterranean Strategy for Underwater Noise Monitoring*, [Resolution 7.13](#) (2019) *Updated Commitments on Underwater Noise and Marine Mammal Protection*, [Resolution 8.17](#) (2022) *Strengthening Measures for Underwater Noise Management and Basin-Wide Monitor*.

ACCOBAMS produced three reports prepared as part of the implementation of Resolution 5.15 (2013):

- 1) Anthropogenic noise and marine mammals: review of the effort in addressing the impact of anthropogenic underwater noise in the ACCOBAMS and ASCOBAMS areas (ACCOBAMS-MOP5/2013/Doc 22 Rev1)

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- 2) Implementation of underwater noise mitigation measures by industries: Operational and economical constraints (ACCOBAMSMOP5/2013/Doc23)
- 3) Methodological guide: Guidance on Underwater Noise Mitigation Measures (ACCOBAMS-MOP5/2013/Doc24). The methodological guide has since become a living document, which has been updated regularly by the joint ACCOBAMS/ASCOBANS/CMS Noise Working Group, with the most recent update produced in 2022 (ACCOBAMS-MOP8/2022/Inf44).

The **Agreement on the Conservation of Small Cetaceans of the Baltic, Northeast Atlantic, Irish and North Seas (ASCOBANS)** followed shortly behind ACCOBAMS, developing [Resolution No. 4](#) (2006) on 'Adverse Effects of Sound, Vessels and Other Forms of Disturbance on Small Cetaceans', where they noted the adverse effects of sound on cetaceans. **ASCOBANS began addressing underwater noise formally in 2008**, when it created an Intersessional Working Group on the Assessment of Acoustic Disturbance. This group examined human activities causing noise disturbance and developed best practice guidelines for mitigation. These early efforts focused on activities such as naval sonar, seismic surveys, and pile-driving. Subsequently, ASCOBANS adopted [Resolution 6.2](#) in 2009, which specifically targeted noise from offshore construction for renewable energy production. The group has also produced guidelines on reducing noise for other marine activities such [Resolution 10.6](#) Mitigating the Impacts of Recreational Activities on Small Cetaceans.

These ASCOBANS and ACCOBAMS **resolutions**, adopted by their respective Meetings of the Parties, are **intended to guide parties** in implementing agreed measures and reporting on their progress. However, they **lack formal enforcement mechanisms**, relying instead on peer review and compliance monitoring processes to encourage adherence.

The Convention on Migratory Species (CMS), also known as the **Bonn Convention**, is a global treaty under the **UN Environment Programme (UNEP)** dedicated to conserving migratory animals and their habitats across national borders, providing a platform for governments to coordinate actions for species like birds, bats, turtles and cetaceans. Unlike the conventions mentioned previously, this convention applies to migratory species across marine, freshwater, and terrestrial habitats. Because many migratory animals move across multiple ecosystems during their life cycles, CMS provides an international framework that supports conservation efforts wherever these species travel, feed, breed, or rest. By recognising the interconnected nature of these habitats, the Convention helps countries coordinate actions to reduce threats, safeguard migratory routes, and preserve the ecological integrity of diverse environments

The CMS first formally recognised anthropogenic underwater noise as a conservation threat in 2008, when the Conference of the Parties (COP9) adopted its initial [Resolution 9.19](#) 'Adverse Anthropogenic Marine/Ocean Noise Impacts on Cetaceans and Other Biota', acknowledging that sonar, seismic surveys, and shipping posed serious risks to migratory species. This was strengthened in 2011 at COP10 with [Resolution 10.24](#) 'Further Steps to Abate Underwater Noise Pollution for the Protection of Cetaceans and Other Migratory Species', urging Parties to integrate noise into environmental assessments. A major milestone came in 2017, when COP12 adopted [Resolution 12.14](#) 'Adverse Impacts of Anthropogenic Noise on Cetaceans and Other Migratory Species', which explicitly defined underwater noise

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as a form of *energy pollution* and detailed its impacts on cetaceans and other migratory species, ranging from behavioural disturbance to injury and mortality. This Resolution also endorsed the CMS Family Guidelines on Environmental Impact Assessments for Marine Noise-Generating Activities, providing Parties with a systematic, science-based framework for assessing and mitigating noise impacts. Whilst this resolution primarily covers marine noise, the resolution's scope (other migratory species) covers **anadromous species** like salmon, eels, sturgeons, and shads where they are CMS-listed and where noise affects their key habitats (estuaries, channels, river mouths).

Throughout the early 2020s, CMS expanded its technical and regulatory influence. In **2020–2025**, CMS Parties reported on the implementation of Resolution 12.14 and advanced work through the **Joint Noise Working Group** with ACCOBAMS and ASCOBANS. In **2025**, CMS published updated progress for COP15 (2026), reaffirming the importance of earlier decisions (14.44–14.47) and promoting the use of [Technical Series No. 46](#), which outlines Best Available Technology (BAT) and Best Environmental Practice (BEP) for reducing noise from shipping, seismic surveys, and pile driving. Parties were encouraged to integrate this guidance into marine spatial planning, licensing, and EIA processes, and to identify gaps, such as the need for guidance for freshwater cetaceans.

The **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)** is an international treaty adopted at the Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 to address the accelerating loss of biodiversity. It has recognised underwater noise as a threat to marine biodiversity, especially to cetaceans and other sensitive species. CBD COP Decision X/29 (Marine and Coastal Biodiversity, 2010) explicitly mentions underwater noise as a pressure on marine biodiversity. It recognises that anthropogenic underwater noise can negatively affect marine and coastal species, and requests the Executive Secretary, in collaboration with Parties, other Governments, and relevant organisations, to compile and synthesise available scientific information on anthropogenic underwater noise and its impacts on marine and coastal biodiversity and habitats.

CBD COP Decision XII/23 (2014) then goes on to further highlight that anthropogenic underwater noise is a significant pressure on marine and coastal biodiversity and urging Parties to avoid, minimize, and mitigate adverse impacts of underwater noise on marine species and ecosystems, characterize noise sources and intensities to better understand impacts, integrate noise considerations into Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), and promote research and monitoring to fill knowledge gaps.

The CBD Technical Series No. 99 (2022) '*Review of the Impacts of Anthropogenic Underwater Noise on Marine Biodiversity and Approaches to Manage and Mitigate Them*' reviews scientific evidence on noise impacts across marine organisms and encourages regional cooperation and best practices for noise mitigation. It suggests mitigation strategies such as vessel design improvements, ship operational measures such as speed reduction and changes to shipping routes, and the use of noise-reducing technologies such as bubble curtains to reduce noise from operations such as underwater construction (e.g. pile driving).

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Whilst these decisions and guidance focus on underwater noise in marine and coastal ecosystems, they (e.g. Decision XII/23, The Technical Series 99) recognise underwater noise as a form of anthropogenic pressure that can affect a wide range of taxa, including fish and invertebrates, which also dominate freshwater ecosystems. This provides the scientific justification and policy mechanisms for countries to address underwater noise in rivers, lakes, wetlands, and estuaries, ensuring that freshwater species and ecosystems are included within broader biodiversity protection measures.

The **Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF)** is a global agreement adopted in December 2022 at the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) COP15. It sets the overarching international strategy for halting and reversing biodiversity loss by 2030, with a long-term vision of “living in harmony with nature” by 2050. Target 7 of the GBF explicitly broadens the definition of pollution to include energy-based, such as underwater noise. Target 7 requires Parties to reduce all forms of pollution to levels that are “not harmful to biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services,” with particular attention to cumulative impacts. This represents a shift in global biodiversity governance, acknowledging the growing evidence that anthropogenic noise alters behaviour, physiology, community structure, and ecological interactions across terrestrial, freshwater, and marine systems.

UNCLOS (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, 1982) provides a comprehensive global framework for addressing marine pollution. Its broad definition of “pollution” in Article 1(4) includes the introduction of substances or energy into the marine environment that could harm marine life or interfere with legitimate uses of the sea. Under Article 192, States have a general obligation to protect and preserve the marine environment, while Article 194 requires them to prevent, reduce, and control pollution from any source, including measures to minimise harmful effects from human activities. Although LNP are not explicitly mentioned, their inclusion may become more prominent in the future.

The **International Maritime Organization (IMO)** addresses NP from ships, recognising that underwater radiated noise from commercial shipping can harm marine life, especially marine mammals. The *2023 IMO Revised Guidelines for the Reduction of Underwater Radiated Noise from Shipping* (MEPC.1/Circ.906) suggest Member States reduce underwater noise through a combination of design, operational, and maintenance measures, applied across the ship’s lifecycle.

The **Ramsar Convention**, formally known as the **Convention on Wetlands of International Importance Especially as Waterfowl Habitat**, is a global environmental treaty adopted in **1971** in the city of *Ramsar*, Iran. Europe currently has 1105 designated Ramsar sites in December 2025 (<https://rsis.ramsar.org/?f%5B0%5D=region+en+s%3AEurope>), the majority of which are freshwater sites. Under the Strategic Framework and guidelines for the future development of the List of Wetlands of International Importance ([Resolution XI.8 Annex 2](#)), Light and noise are included as factors (actual or likely) to adversely affect a site’s ecological character. Under [Resolution X.17](#), Ramsar Parties are required to apply biodiversity-inclusive mandatory use of Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) and Strategic Environmental Assessments (SEA) processes, drawing directly on expanded guidance from the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). These assessments must evaluate all forms of disturbance affecting wetland biodiversity.

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The **UNECE Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (the Water Convention 1992)** is an international environmental treaty, designed to promote the sustainable management, protection, and cooperative governance of shared freshwater resources. The Convention requires Parties to “take all appropriate measures to prevent, control and reduce any transboundary impact” affecting shared rivers, lakes, or aquifers, with “transboundary impact” defined broadly to include adverse effects on flora, fauna, water quality, ecosystems, and human health. Whilst it doesn’t explicitly mention LNP, it provides an obligation to prevent and reduce all transboundary impacts and could be applied to LNP if ecological harm is demonstrated.

Several international conventions have developed guidance and regulatory measures to reduce the impacts of anthropogenic underwater noise, although many of these instruments remain focused on marine environments. As a result, freshwater systems receive comparatively little policy attention. Sites protected under the Ramsar Convention are provided a binding procedural mechanism that obliges Parties to evaluate and mitigate underwater noise whenever it poses risks to wetland ecosystems and the migratory species they support.

Strengthening international governance to explicitly address underwater noise in rivers, lakes, and wetlands represents a critical next step. Integrating freshwater-specific considerations into existing biodiversity and wetland frameworks would help ensure that the ecological consequences of underwater noise are recognised and mitigated across all aquatic domains, not only the marine realm. The CBD and the GBF within it provide instruments that can be used to strengthen the governance of underwater noise across all aquatic habitats.

4.2 LIGHT POLLUTION

The principal **driver of international regulatory action on LP** and its impacts on the environment and biodiversity has been the **Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS)**. Since 2017, CMS has progressively advanced measures to protect migratory species from the adverse effects of ALAN. Several key instruments have since been adopted, including [Resolution 8.6 ‘Bats and Light Pollution’](#), adopted at the 8th Meeting of the Parties (MoP) to EUROBATS, held in Monte Carlo, Monaco (8–10 October 2018; Voight et al. 2018). This was followed by [Resolution 13.5 Light Pollution Guidelines for Wildlife and its Annex](#), adopted at CMS COP13 in Gandhinagar in February 2020, which incorporated the Australian national guidelines as a foundational reference ([UNEP/CMS/Resolution 13.5](#)). CMS subsequently expanded its evidence base through the [Summary of Preliminary Findings of a Review of the Information Available on the Impact of Light Pollution on Different Taxa of Migratory Species](#), presented to the 5th Meeting of the Sessional Committee of the CMS Scientific Council (ScC-SC5), held online from 28 June to 9 July 2021 (UNEP/CMS/ScC-SC5/Inf.7).

The most recent development is the adoption of the International Light Pollution Guidelines ([UNEP/CMS/Resolution 13.5 \(Rev.COP14\)/Annex](#)). These guidelines provide detailed recommendations for **incorporating ALAN into Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)** to prevent or mitigate adverse effects on a wide range of migratory species, including those inhabiting freshwater and marine environments. Collectively, the CMS instruments adopted

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since 2017 demonstrate an increasingly robust recognition of the ecological significance of LP and its relevance to the conservation of migratory species across diverse taxa.

Figure 2: Flow chart describing the environmental impact assessment process developed under the CMS International Light Pollution Guidelines. Source: International Light Pollution Guidelines (UNEP/CMS/Resolution 13.5 (Rev.COP14)/Annex⁷), page 9.

Another important international framework contributing to efforts to reduce LP is the **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)**. The **Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF)**, which sets ambitious global conservation targets, includes **Target 7**, calling for **pollution from all sources** to be reduced to levels that **are not harmful to biodiversity by 2030 (CBD, 2022)**. This target specifically references excess nutrients, pesticide risks, and plastic pollution. Although the GBF **does not explicitly mention** light or noise pollution, the accompanying [CBD guidance document](#) clarifies that “all sources of pollution” are to be considered within the scope of Target 7, **explicitly including light and noise**. Parties are therefore encouraged to address these forms of pollution with the same level of commitment as other well-recognised environmental pressures.

Similar to NP, **UNCLOS** can also be interpreted as **applicable to the reduction of LP** impacts on marine and potentially on freshwater habitats. Its definition of “*marine pollution*” expressly

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https://www.cms.int/sites/default/files/document/cms_cop14_res.13.5_rev.cop14_annex_cm_s-international-light-pollution-guidelines_e_0.pdf

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includes the introduction of energy into the marine environment, thereby creating a legal basis for interpreting the Convention's provisions as relevant to both forms of LNP. This interpretation provides a potential pathway for integrating LNP considerations into broader obligations to prevent, reduce, and control marine pollution (Yakushina, 2025a).

Another important international organisation engaged in bringing emerging environmental pressures onto the global policy agenda and in recognising the significance of natural darkness for biodiversity and ecosystem health is the **International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)**. The IUCN has recently adopted two significant documents relevant to LP: [The World at Night: Preserving Natural Darkness for Heritage Conservation and Night Sky Appreciation](#) (2024) and [Motion 046: Global Strategy for Natural Darkness Restoration: Protecting Key Habitats and Mitigating Light Pollution](#). The World at Night is a comprehensive report that highlights the urgent need to address the adverse impacts of LP on biodiversity and habitats. In the aquatic context, the report identifies a wide range of ecological effects associated with ALAN and emphasises the importance of protecting these environments from artificial illumination. Motion 46, by contrast, is a policy-oriented instrument that calls on countries and stakeholders to undertake coordinated action to safeguard nocturnal environments more broadly, irrespective of habitat type. It underscores the ecological value of natural darkness across species and ecosystems and promotes the development of global strategies to restore and preserve dark habitats. Together, these IUCN initiatives reflect a growing international momentum towards recognising natural darkness as a critical environmental resource and integrating light pollution mitigation into global biodiversity conservation efforts.

Attention to LP on the international agenda is steadily increasing, with the issue being discussed in a range of global fora and referenced across several international initiatives, including the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) COP16 [“Restoring the Night” event](#) (18/11/2025 organised by ABEMA, UFMG, SEMIL-SP, and [PLAN-B project](#)), the [2007 Declaration in Defence of the Night Sky and the Right to Starlight](#) (La Palma Declaration), and the [Sustainable Development Goal 18 initiative](#). Although these efforts primarily promote the protection of the night environment more broadly, they nonetheless **offer direct benefits for the conservation of marine and freshwater ecosystems** by helping to reduce the pervasive impacts of ALAN on biodiversity.

However, despite this growing recognition, there remains a clear **need for a more formal and binding acknowledgement of natural darkness as a critical environmental value**, particularly in relation to the health and functioning of marine and freshwater environments (Yakushina, 2025).

5. REGIONAL SEAS CONVENTIONS

The Regional Seas Programme of the UN Environment Programme (UNEP) is a key initiative for the conservation and sustainable use of marine resources. It operates through Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans (RSCAPs), which are legally binding agreements among countries sharing a common body of water (Rochette et al. 2015). The RSCAPs provide inter-governmental frameworks to address the degradation of the oceans and seas at a regional level, initially focussing on pollution at sea and land-based sources of pollution ([UNEP regional seas programme](#)).

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Within Europe there are four main conventions (Figure 3):

- Barcelona Convention focussing on the Mediterranean Sea
- Bucharest Convention focussing on the Black Sea
- Helsinki Convention (HELCOM) focussing on the Baltic Sea
- OSPAR Convention (OSPAR) focussing on the North East Atlantic

Figure 3: Extent of Regional Seas Conventions and the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) of EU Member States in European waters. Note that the northern boundary of the OSPAR maritime area extends to 90 degrees North.

5.1 BARCELONA CONVENTION

The Barcelona Convention, formally the *Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean*, is a regional environmental treaty adopted in 1976 under the UNEP Mediterranean Action Plan. Its main goal is to prevent, reduce, and eliminate pollution in the Mediterranean Sea and protect coastal ecosystems, contributing to sustainable development.

A number of the Barcelona Convention's adopted decisions provide an important governance foundation that can support future management of LNP. The Convention's shift toward an

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ecosystem approach (Decision IG 17/6), including the adoption of **Good Environmental Status (GES) 11 ecological objectives** corresponding to the vision and strategic goals (Annex II / Decision IG.21/3). One of those objectives is EO11: Energy, including underwater noise. This objective complements D11 of the MSFD, and is currently focused on ensuring that *'Noise from human activities causes no significant impact on marine and coastal ecosystems'*. EO11 supports regional cooperation for monitoring and mitigation of underwater noise, complementing MSFD requirements in the Mediterranean region. The ecological objectives are policy guidance tools and are therefore not binding.

This is strengthened by the **Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme (IMAP)** and its related assessment criteria ([Decision IG.22/7](#)), which expand the region's capacity to track human pressures on marine ecosystems. Sectoral decisions also play a role: the **Regional Strategy for the Prevention of and Response to Marine Pollution from Ships (2016–2021)** ([Decision IG.22/4](#)) and the **Guidelines concerning pleasure craft activities (Decision IG 17/9)** help address vessel-related pressures, creating policy space that could extend to noise reduction measures. Likewise, the **Mediterranean Offshore Action Plan (Decision IG.22/3)** provides a regulatory mechanism for controlling pollution from offshore exploration and extraction activities, many of which are significant sources of underwater noise.

Updates to several **regional Action Plans**, including those for **Cetaceans, Coralligenous and other calcareous bioconcretions**, and **Species Introductions and Invasive Species**, alongside the mandates to revise the **Action Plan on Marine and Coastal Birds** and the **Reference List of Marine and Coastal Habitat Types**—further reinforce the Convention's ecological commitments by identifying sensitive species and habitats that may be vulnerable to noise or artificial light. Broader strategic frameworks such as the **Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development 2016–2025** (Decision IG.22/2), the **UNEP/MAP Mid-Term Strategy 2016–2021** (Decision IG.22/1), and the **programme of work and budget** (Decision IG.22/20) ensure long-term institutional support for addressing emerging pollutants. Meanwhile, regional coordination mechanisms, particularly through the **Regional Activity Centre for Specially Protected Areas (RAC/SPA)** and cooperation provisions under Decision IG.22/18—enhance collective capacity to integrate light and noise considerations into spatial planning, protected-area management, and regional policy development. Collectively, these decisions position the Barcelona Convention to incorporate light and noise pollution more explicitly in future updates, even if direct regulatory measures have yet to be adopted.

Regional monitoring and assessment of impulsive noise in the Mediterranean was carried out under ACCOBAMS project (Maglio et al. 2015), and subsequently under the [QUIETMED](#) project, whilst monitoring of continuous noise was coordinated under the [SOUNDSCAPE](#) project

The Barcelona Convention has also produced guidance to reduce the impact of noise pollution from different sectors, as well as to reduce the impact on different species groups. Guidelines for pleasure craft state that authorities should set maximum sound levels, that the technical specifications of the pleasure craft's engine comply with the standards for noise emissions

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required by the relevant national and/or European legislation, and that users should reduce speed in areas of significant wildlife populations (Annex I: REMPEC/WG.28/7).

5.2 BUCHAREST CONVENTION

The Bucharest Convention, officially known as the Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution was adopted in 1992. Six contracting parties are involved: Bulgaria, Georgia, Romania, Russia, Turkey and Ukraine. The Convention aims to prevent, reduce and control pollution in the Black Sea. Regional monitoring has yet to be undertaken in the Black Sea, although there was work towards establishing a regional noise registry within the [CeNoBS](#) (Cetacean Noise and Bycatch) project. Furthermore, in 2025 ACCOBAMS released a [data call](#) on noise data in the Mediterranean and Black Sea regions to support the implementation of MSFD.

5.3 HELCOM CONVENTION

The Helsinki Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area was originally signed in 1974, but has been subject to amendments in 1992 and 2014. Currently, there are 10 contracting parties: Denmark, Estonia, EU, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Russia and Sweden. In 2013, HELCOM agreed that the level of ambient and the distribution of impulsive sounds in the Baltic Sea should not have a negative impact on marine life and that mitigation measures should be put in place. Therefore, an expert group was established to prepare and facilitate the implementation of a roadmap to build a knowledge based on underwater noise. The Life+ project [BIAS](#) (Baltic Sea Information on the Acoustic Soundscape) and [HELCOM BLUES](#) (Biodiversity, Litter, Underwater noise and Effective regional measures for the Baltic Sea) project produced baseline soundscape maps for the region.

In 2021, the HELCOM [regional action plan](#) on underwater noise was adopted, becoming the first action plan on noise in the European Seas. The Action Plan contains both regional and national actions that focus on the reduction of pressures and impacts from underwater noise sources of different types.

5.4 OSPAR CONVENTION

The OSPAR Convention, officially known as the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North East Atlantic, was adopted in 1992. It aims to protect and conserve the marine environment in the North East Atlantic region and entered into force in 1998. OSPAR is actively addressing NP in the North East Atlantic region through various initiatives.

An ambient noise monitoring strategy was adopted in 2015 combining measurement stations and model efforts to generate estimates of noise across the North Sea basin. The EU-funded JOMOPANS (Joint Monitoring of Ambient Noise in the North Sea) project ([JOMOPANS, Interreg VB North Sea Region Programme](#)) developed a framework for a fully operational joint monitoring programme, providing tools for managers, planners and other stakeholders to incorporate the effects of ambient noise in their environmental assessments. OSPAR also undertook its first regional assessment of impulsive noise in 2017 as part of an intermediate assessment of the state of the North East Atlantic. That assessment was further updated in

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2019, allowing for multi-year assessment. Impulsive noises are generally regulated through national licensing therefore an Impulsive Noise Registry was developed to store data and produce a regional assessment. In terms of mitigation measures, in 2024, OSPAR published a report and inventory of measures to mitigate the emission and environmental impact of underwater noise ([OSPAR 2024](#)).

In 2025, OSPAR adopted a dedicated Regional Action Plan (RAP) ([OSPAR 2025](#)) to reduce anthropogenic NP to levels that do not adversely affect the marine environment. The action plan will be implemented from 2025 to 2035, targeting 8 prioritised actions:

- Targets and thresholds
- Spatial planning
- Commercial shipping
- Geophysical surveys
- Construction and operation of marine infrastructure
- UXO (Unexploded Ordnance) disposal
- Other underwater noise sources
- Outreach and engagement

LNP is still undeveloped in the Regional Seas Conventions, which were historically designed to respond to traditional pollution issues like oil spills, hazardous waste, nutrients, and land-based sources of pollution. Many have since broadened their scope to include emerging pressures, reflecting their mandate to address regional environmental threats collaboratively. Conventions regularly update their action plans and protocols to reflect changing priorities, and increasingly acknowledge the ecological impacts of underwater noise, often in coordination with the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Improving monitoring frameworks and biodiversity indicators helps countries better identify and quantify LNP pressures on sensitive species and ecosystems. Regional Seas Conventions such as OSPAR and HELCOM have begun integrating noise into monitoring and ecosystem-based strategies, but concrete regulatory measures remain limited. Light pollution is almost entirely absent from binding instruments across the Regional Seas system, receiving little formal recognition despite its growing ecological significance. There is an urgent need for stronger, more explicit acknowledgement of both pollutants within these conventions. Meaningful progress will require coordinated action by Parties, supported by clearer mandates and more robust regulatory mechanisms.

The MSFD requires Member States to work together when developing their marine strategies, placing strong emphasis on regional cooperation. In particular, Articles 6 and 8 call for the use of [Regional Sea Conventions](#) to coordinate marine strategies and carry out initial environmental assessments, ensuring that evaluations of marine status are consistent, comprehensive, and regionally coherent. This could be further strengthened by the UNEP [Regional Seas Programme](#); a global flagship programme implemented through regional frameworks for cooperation, management and protection of shared marine and coastal environments, which may help strengthen and harmonize approaches to monitor and mitigate LNP across regions.

6. EU FRAMEWORKS RELATING TO LNP

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In the **European Union**, the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive** (Directive 2008/56/EC) (MSFD) is the EU's main legislative instrument for achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) in marine waters. In 2008, underwater NP was included as the eleventh Descriptor:

“Introduction of energy, including underwater noise, is at levels that do not adversely affect the marine environment.”

At the time, the MSFD presented a pioneering recognition of the impacts of manmade noise on aquatic life, identifying noise for the first time in legislation as a form of pollution, and signalling an unprecedented willingness on the part of lawmakers to address the issue directly and explicitly (Merchant et al. 2022).

Following the adoption of the MSFD in 2008 ([Directive 2008/56/EC](#)), various working groups were convened during 2009 and 2010 to define quantitative indicators to be used for the assessment of each Descriptor (Borja et al. 2011). Task Group 11 prepared advice on underwater noise (Figure 4; Tasker et al. 2010), recommending the adoption of three indicators, which would cover: (i) low and mid-frequency impulsive sound (e.g. seismic airguns, explosions, pile driving); (ii) high frequency impulsive sounds (e.g. echosounders and other high-frequency sonar); (iii) low frequency continuous sound (mainly shipping). Of these, Task Group 11 advised that indicators (i) and (iii) were the most important. These two indicators were adopted by the European Commission in 2010 (European Commission 2010), hereafter denoted D11.1 (impulsive noise) and D11.2 (continuous noise).

Figure 4: Timeline of the development of the MSFD Descriptor 11 and technical guidance published by scientific advisory groups.

The MSFD has stimulated a concerted research effort across Europe to develop monitoring programmes and to conduct research towards specifying threshold values, which would define ‘Good Environmental Status (GES)’ for underwater noise. **Programmes of Measures (PoMs)** submitted by Member States **under Descriptor 11 of the MSFD** (Article 13) focus primarily on **underwater noise**. Monitoring actions include establishing marine noise registries and characterising the acoustic environment. Several Member States have introduced mitigation measures, such as guidelines and codes of conduct, to reduce noise during the construction and operation of offshore installations, shipping, port activities, explosive ordnance disposal, and recreational boating. Protecting marine mammals and cetaceans is frequently highlighted as a priority.

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In contrast, few Member States have detailed **PoMs addressing LP**. **Germany** lists ‘*Development and application of environmentally friendly lighting for offshore installations*’ as one of its PoMs for Article 13 of the MSFD, whilst the **Netherlands** lists ‘*Limitation of platform lighting on oil and gas platforms*’ and **Malta** lists ‘*Restrictions on use of light by navigating vessels within buffer zones surrounding protected breeding grounds*’.

The **Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP)**, adopted in 2021 as part of the European Green Deal, aims to **reduce pollution to levels that are no longer harmful to human health and ecosystems by 2050**. They committed to establishing EU-wide **threshold** values for **underwater noise** from shipping, construction, dredging, and offshore activities. In 2022, these thresholds were established (Directorate-General of the Environment, 2022); no more than 20% of a given marine area can be exposed to continuous underwater noise over a year, whilst no more than 20% of a marine habitat can be exposed to impulsive noise over a given day, and no more than 10% over a year. These thresholds must be integrated into marine strategies under the MSFD.

ALAN is not yet a formal MSFD descriptor, but it is increasingly recognised as an emerging pressure under D11 because it represents an energy input similar to noise. LP is recognised as an environmental issue under the Nature Restoration Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991) (NRR), the Zero Pollution Action Plan (COM/2021/400), the Light Pollution Manifesto (Yakushina et al., 2023), the [Light Pollution Policy Brief](#) (Yakushina et al., 2025c) and the [Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Report](#) (EEA-JRC, 2025), suggesting that it may likely be incorporated in future cycles as part of D11’s energy inputs affecting marine ecosystems.

The **NRR**, adopted in 2024, is the **EU’s first Europe-wide law mandating restoration** of degraded ecosystems, which sets time-bound targets for restoring degraded habitats. For **marine habitats**, its primary focus is on **habitat recovery**, biodiversity enhancement, and climate resilience. Recital 49 of the Preamble of the NRR acknowledges that artificial light negatively impacts biodiversity, and that Member States should consider measures to stop, reduce, or remediate LP in all ecosystems when preparing their national restoration plans. In **Annex VII, example mitigation measures for LNP** are given, although the measure for underwater NP is only directed towards marine habitats. Member States must prepare National Restoration Plans (NRPs) by 2026, which can include measures to address pressures that hinder restoration goals. If LP or NP is identified as a significant pressure on species or habitats (e.g. aquatic insects, fish migration), mitigation actions could be incorporated at the national level, although the preamble is not binding and implementing these actions would be voluntary.

The **NRR prioritises improving the condition of existing Natura 2000 areas until 2030** and setting legally binding restoration targets for degraded ecosystems (20% of EU land and sea by 2030). Natura 2000 sites are designated to ensure the long-term survival of specific species and habitats of European importance by maintaining or restoring them to a “*favourable conservation status*”. The network of sites is composed of two types of designated areas under two main EU laws: Special Areas of Conservation (SACs): designated under the **Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC)** to protect rare, endangered, or vulnerable natural habitats (e.g., reefs, coastal lagoons, estuaries) and species other than birds (e.g., seals, dolphins, salmon). And

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Special Protection Areas (SPAs), classified under the **Birds Directive (2009/147/EC)** to protect core breeding, resting, and wintering sites for rare or migratory bird species. Article 6.2 of the Habitats Directive addresses the protection of Natura 2000 sites and requires Member States to prevent deterioration of habitats and significant disturbance of species for which the site is designated. This includes managing the impact of NP in marine environments within these protected areas. There is no specific mention of LP. Whilst no mention of LNP in the Birds Directive, Article 4.4 states that *'Member States shall take appropriate steps to avoid pollution or deterioration of habitats or any disturbances affecting the birds, in so far as these would be significant.'* Whilst there is no mention of LP, Member States can face infringement proceedings and fines for not implementing legally required conservation actions. For example, in [case C-504/14, the European Court of Justice](#) ruled that Greece breached its obligations under the Natura 2000 legal framework by failing to adopt measures to protect sea turtles from threats such as LP in Kyparissia Bay.

Under Article 6(3) of the Habitats Directive, any plan or project that could significantly affect a Natura 2000 site must undergo an appropriate assessment. The **Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (2011/92/EU, amended by 2014/52/EU)** complements this by ensuring that Natura 2000 sites are protected from potential impacts, including LNP, through its mandatory assessment process for projects likely to have significant environmental effects. The EIA must include a description of the project, including in particular: an estimate, by type and quantity, of expected residues and emissions (water, air and soil pollution, noise, vibration, light, heat, radiation, etc.), resulting from the operation of the proposed project (Annex IV), although mitigation measures do not have to be included. However, in practice, LNP do not currently receive much attention within the EIA.

The Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) (Directive 2014/89/EU) does not set environmental quality standards or mention LNP directly itself, but it can play a large role in regulating LNP in the marine environment. It provides the planning framework to organise human activities so that MSFDs can achieve GES in EU marine waters. It takes an **ecosystem-based approach** to allocate maritime space for activities like shipping, offshore wind, and fisheries. Noise thresholds from the MSFD can be integrated into marine plans by ensuring that MSFD noise maps and registries model cumulative noise and incorporate this into MSP scenarios.

The Water Framework Directive (WFD) (Directive 2000/60 EC) establishes a legal framework for the protection and sustainable management of groundwater and inland, transitional (estuaries) and coastal surface waters up to one mile from shore. Its main goal is to improve water quality by requiring all water bodies to reach "good ecological status" or, for heavily modified waters, "good ecological potential". This includes preventing deterioration, reducing pollution, and ensuring sustainable water use. LNP are not managed under this directive.

The Eighth Environmental Action Programme (Decision (EU) 2022/591) is the EU's main framework for environmental and climate action up to 2030, aiming to achieve a well-being economy in which people live within planetary boundaries by 2050. Building on the European Green Deal, it sets six priority objectives for 2030, including climate neutrality, a circular economy, zero pollution, and biodiversity protection. The 8th EAP explicitly includes light and

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noise pollution as pressures under the “zero-pollution” objective, and establishes a framework for tracking pollution trends, including non-chemical pressures. Whilst this sounds promising, it recognises LNP as pressures, it does not actively monitor either, with no headline indicators for either pressures.

LNP also started to receive more attention within the EU political discussion. **LNP have a dedicated section in the Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Report (EEA-JRC, 2025).** This highlights that specific **legislation for LP remains limited**, and that **no specific EU targets or binding measures for reducing ALAN** have been proposed. The report stresses the need for concrete actions beyond awareness campaigns. For **NP**, the report highlights that **noise is already regulated with binding thresholds under MSFD**; still a significant challenge **requiring stricter enforcement**.

The **EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (COM(2020) 380)** notes that **pollution is a major driver of biodiversity loss**, including **underwater noise**. There is **no direct mention of LP**. The strategy has two key aims: to protect 30% of EU land and sea areas by 2030 and to introduce legally binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems. The NRR is considered one of its key legislative instruments, which operationalises the restoration targets set in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, ensuring Member States implement concrete measures through National Restoration Plans.

The **non-government-led initiatives**, such as the [European Light Pollution Manifesto](#) (Yakushina et al., 2023) and the [Light Pollution Policy Brief](#) (Yakushina et al., 2025c) call for coordinated EU action, among the other, to: 1) legally recognise ALAN as a pollutant, as well as an important value of the night as a part of nature; 2) set measurable targets to reduce LP; 3) integrate LP into environmental monitoring frameworks; 4) mitigate ecological impacts through responsible lighting practices and energy-efficient solutions; 5) provide open-access lighting data to support transparency and evidence-based policymaking.

EU regulatory instruments for addressing LNP in freshwater systems remain less developed than those for marine environments. Most European freshwater directives place strong emphasis on safeguarding human health by ensuring that water used for drinking, bathing, and domestic purposes is safe and clean. Freshwater pollution control is primarily governed by the Water Framework Directive (WFD), which focuses on maintaining chemical and ecological status. In contrast, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) addresses both chemical and physical pressures to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES). While the WFD requires Member States to identify significant pressures affecting ecological status, evidence that LNP impacts biological quality elements, such as fish behaviour or macroinvertebrate communities, could allow these pressures to be formally recognised and potentially managed within the WFD framework. If LNP is shown to cause significant disturbance in marine or freshwater protected areas (Natura 2000 sites), management could occur through the Habitats and Birds Directives, alongside the NRR, which prioritises Natura 2000 sites before expanding after 2030.

7. NATIONAL REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS

Regulatory frameworks to address LNP at the national level are generally **more developed** than those at the international or EU levels, as these forms of pollution **first began to receive sustained attention primarily within domestic regulatory contexts**.

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NP regulatory frameworks across **EU Member States**, in particular, are shaped by a combination of EU-level obligations and nationally tailored implementation measures, resulting in a regulatory landscape that is coherent in its overarching objectives yet heterogeneous in practice. The cornerstone instrument is the **END** (2002/49/EC), which **obliges Member States to assess ambient noise** through strategic noise mapping, designate quiet areas, and prepare **noise action plans** aimed at preventing and reducing harmful exposure. While the END provides a harmonised framework, it allows considerable discretion regarding the establishment of limit values, the choice of mitigation strategies, and enforcement mechanisms. Consequently, **national approaches vary substantially**: some countries, such as Germany and the Netherlands, have adopted comprehensive limit-value systems and long-term noise management strategies, whereas others rely more heavily on local or sector-specific measures, particularly in relation to transport, industry, and urban planning. Many **Member States have incorporated noise considerations into broader policy contexts**, such as public-health policies, yet the degree of integration and the robustness of monitoring and reporting remain uneven across the EU. A further **limitation** is that most **national noise regulations continue to prioritise the protection of human health**, with comparatively **little attention** paid to the **environmental and ecological impacts of noise**.

One of the **key national-level measures to reduce NP**, while also generating benefits for the environment, is the establishment of “**quiet**” **green areas**. A “quiet area” is generally understood as a place with a pleasant soundscape in which noise, or unwanted sound, is absent or not dominant (EEA, 2025). Such areas typically include parks, green spaces, forests, agricultural land, water bodies, and brownfield sites. Although their **primary purpose is to protect human health and well-being**, these measures can also **provide significant ecological benefits** by creating refuges from anthropogenic noise and enhancing habitat quality for wildlife. Overall, while **EU legislation offers a shared framework for action**, the **effectiveness of NP regulation ultimately depends on national action**, and the extent to which noise is recognised not only as a public-health issue but also as an environmental concern.

As a result, the effects of anthropogenic noise on ecosystems and biodiversity, particularly within marine and freshwater habitats, are addressed only marginally or remain absent altogether from national regulatory frameworks. **Further national developments are needed to address the impacts of NP specifically on the environment and biodiversity.**

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Figure 5. Screenshot from the AquaPLAN risk map on combined impacts of light and noise pollution in marine habitats (<https://aquaplan.eofrom.space/>).

Similar to NP, **LP regulation is advancing more rapidly at the national level** than at other political scales (Yakushina, 2024). An increasing number of **European countries have begun adopting regulatory measures to address the impacts of ALAN on the environment and biodiversity**, with France, Germany, and Croatia among the most prominent examples (Yakushina et al., 2024). France, in particular, has introduced a series of regulatory instruments that either integrate LP into broader environmental frameworks or address it through dedicated legislation, including the Decree on the Prevention and Limitation of Light Pollution (2011), the Decree on Night Lighting of Non-Residential Buildings (2013), and the Decree on the Prevention, Reduction and Limitation of Light Pollution (2018). These measures establish a range of **technical lighting requirements and restrictions**, some of which **apply directly to freshwater and marine environments**. For instance, French legislation prohibits direct illumination of rivers, lakes, ponds, and coastal or maritime zones, and requires new coastal lighting installations to be oriented away from the sea or equipped with shielding to prevent light spill into marine areas.

Germany has pursued an approach centred on **amending existing national environmental legislation** to incorporate measures that **directly address** the impacts of **ALAN** by balancing between emission regulation and immission control (Hölker et al. 2021). In 2021, a new paragraph (§ 41a) was implemented in the Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG) that explicitly aims to **protect wild animals and plants from the adverse effects of artificial outdoor lighting**. The ordinance under §54 Abs. 4d BNatSchG has not yet been issued. §41a itself only becomes effective once this ordinance enters into force. With respect to marine and freshwater environments, the ordinance will probably incorporate restrictions **on the direct illumination of water bodies**. Additional **regulations are also emerging at regional and local levels**, with the federal states of Baden-Württemberg and Bavaria developing their own instruments to further limit LP and mitigate ecological impacts.

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Croatia was the **first European country to adopt a comprehensive legal framework** dedicated specifically to **LP**. Its regulatory approach is centred on the Protection Against Light Pollution Act (OG 14/19), which is further operationalised through three implementing ordinances: the Ordinance on Lighting Zones, Permitted Lighting Values and Methods of Managing Lighting Systems (OG 128/20); the Ordinance on the Content, Format and Drafting of the Lighting Plan and Action Plan for the Construction and/or Reconstruction of Outdoor Lighting (OG 22/23); and the Ordinance on Measurement and Monitoring of Environmental Lighting (OG 22/23). Together, these instruments establish **maximum permissible ALAN parameters** and **classify the national territory into defined lighting zones**, each with specific regulatory requirements. Notably, the framework **explicitly** states that **LP protection measures** must include **the protection of natural water bodies**.

Other EU Member States have also begun to introduce ALAN considerations into their regulatory frameworks or have taken steps towards formally recognising LP as an environmental concern, including Austria, Italy, Slovenia, Poland, the Czech Republic, and Portugal. However, despite this growing awareness, national action remains largely uncoordinated and limited in scope, while levels of LP continue to increase annually (Falchi & Bará, 2023). In the **absence of a unified regulatory framework** to address LP, **national measures remain fragmented** and highly **variable**, ranging from technical standards to spatial planning provisions and sector-specific restrictions. This diversity underscores the **need for a more coordinated and coherent approach** at both the **international and EU levels** to ensure effective and consistent action on LP across Europe.

Another important dimension of national regulatory action concerns the **National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs)** and **National Nature Restoration Plans (NNRPs)**. NBSAPs are strategic frameworks through which Parties implement the objectives and targets of the CBD, including those set out in the Kunming-Montreal GBF. Notably, several countries have begun to integrate LNP into their NBSAPs, signalling growing recognition of these pressures within national biodiversity governance. For example, Belgium's recently updated NBSAP highlights the need to investigate, monitor, and **reduce pollution from all sources**, **explicitly** including **LNP**, and notes that these pollutants are often overlooked and require greater attention. Similarly, the Czech Republic's NBSAP identifies **LNP** as a **driver of significant habitat fragmentation**, particularly in relation to **watercourses**, and includes targeted measures such as Measure 6.1.2: Strengthen a unified approach to reducing LP and its negative impacts on wildlife and ecosystems. Malta's NBSAP also **incorporates both forms of pollution** through measures such as Action 8.8, which mandates the development of policy tools and a systematic monitoring regime to address the impacts of LP on biodiversity. **Although these documents** in most cases **do not explicitly refer to freshwater or marine environments**, their **overarching policy goals** are **likely to generate substantive co-benefits for these habitats**.

NNRPs are strategic national documents **prepared by EU Member States** to implement the targets and obligations of the EU NRR, outlining planned measures to restore degraded ecosystems across their territories. Although NNRPs are not due until 1 September 2026, **several countries have already begun developing** them and engaging in public consultations. **Stakeholders** from scientific, environmental, and civil society communities are actively **advocating for the inclusion of specific measures to reduce LNP** and to **restore the night and quiet areas** for the benefit of diverse habitats and biodiversity.

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8. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the **regulatory instruments aimed at addressing LNP remain fragmented and limited**, a gap that is **particularly evident at the EU level**.

Management of underwater noise in marine systems is more comprehensive than ALAN in marine systems or regulation of either pollutant in freshwater systems. Underwater noise is regulated under the MSFD with binding thresholds, monitoring, and mitigation measures. However, gaps still remain. The Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Report (EEA-JRC, 2025) notes that **current measures are insufficient** and calls for stricter enforcement and additional actions to meet zero-pollution targets by 2050. Similarly, the Technical Group on Underwater Noise has urged clear **operational guidance and harmonised enforcement of thresholds** across Member States (Borsani et al., 2023). CBD Technical Guidance No. 99 recommends incorporating noise considerations into marine spatial planning and environmental impact assessments, but, as with the recent European NRR, these recommendations remain voluntary

Currently, there are no binding regulations for LP in any aquatic habitats. Some Member States have introduced voluntary mitigation measures for ALAN in marine environments, such as reducing lighting on offshore platforms, but no binding thresholds exist, and implementation remains inconsistent. Whilst LP is not currently a formal pressure with binding thresholds within the MSFD, there is pressure for it to become so.

With respect to **best practices for strengthening the policy framework for managing and mitigating the impacts of light and noise pollution (LNP) in aquatic habitats**, we **recommend** the following:

- 1) Further **increase our knowledge** on the impacts on unrepresented habitats (i.e., coastal, freshwater), species and populations in the aquatic environment to help improve future policy implementation.
- 2) Establish **harmonised, species-appropriate standards** for measuring underwater sound and artificial light assessing biological responses, and evaluating mitigation effectiveness.
- 3) **Align objectives** of international frameworks, regional seas conventions and national guidelines.
- 4) **Include light** explicitly under Descriptor 11 of the MSFD and continue to develop thresholds to mitigate the effects of light and noise pollution in the aquatic environment.
- 5) **Classify LNP as environmental pollutants** across all aquatic ecosystems, including both marine and freshwater environments, and ensure their consideration in ecological risk assessments and relevant environmental planning and management instruments at appropriate scales (e.g. river basin management plans).

Further research is needed to properly assess how national actions address light and noise pollution in aquatic ecosystems. Although both marine and freshwater ecosystems are affected by LNP, governance remains uneven across these domains. The MSFD provides the only binding regulatory target for NP but these obligations apply only to marine waters, leaving freshwater systems without equivalent legal requirements. LP is not subject to any binding targets under the MSFD, and LNP in inland and transitional waters are addressed only indirectly, if at all, within existing EU legislation such as the Water Framework Directive. This

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results in a fragmented governance landscape where marine noise is regulated, but freshwater noise and all forms of aquatic light pollution lack enforceable standards.

Current international guidance, such as CBD Technical Guidance No. 99, which encourages integrating underwater noise into spatial planning and impact assessments, offers useful direction but remains entirely voluntary, mirroring the non-binding nature of recent EU measures like the NRR (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991). Notably, both international frameworks and many national policies are now progressing more rapidly on regulating aquatic noise and light pollution than the EU itself, highlighting a growing need for the EU to catch up and strengthen its own regulatory approach.

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These researchers are directly involved in advancing research and policy on light and noise pollution in aquatic environments and their contributions reflect the collaborative expertise of AquaPLAN (coordinated by the University of Pisa and comprising 15 institutions across Europe) and PLAN-B (a sister project focused on biodiversity and environmental governance), ensuring that the scientific and policy outputs are grounded in robust interdisciplinary collaboration

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10. CONTRIBUTIONS

Samantha Garrard: main author, general structure of the document.

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Elena Maggi: general revision.

Alessandro Marchetti: main contribution to sections: Preamble, Introduction, References; specifically overall copyediting and cross-check.

Mascha Stroobant: main contribution to sections: List of Abbreviation, References.

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